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Chemical composition identity of *Lavandula angustifolia* and *Ocimum basilicum* (Lamiales: lamiaceae) extract by Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry

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Abstract

Many medicinal plants can provide us with some natural compounds that could be used as medicine or poison functionalities products. *Lavandula angustifolia* and *Ocimum basilicum* from (Lamiales: lamiaceae) rich in variety of unknown phytochemical compounds could be detected to define its chemical position. Extraction and detection by Gas chromatography and Mass spectrometry carried out and identified some compound. The determination of total terpenoids contents in each extract, results achieved percentage of monoterpenoids 23,20%, diterpenoids 18,16 % and sesquiterpenoids 13,11% for both extracts respectively, also, phenols, acids and fatty acids. Toxicity of both plant extracts against *Drosophila melanogaster* (Meigen) (Drosophilidae: Diptera), tested whereas LC₅₀ values were 257.7, 377 at 24 hrs. of exposure, respectively. Both compounds exhibited fumigant and repellent effects. The concluding results achieved that both extracts were adjacent to each other in the compound detected by Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and to the toxicity effect.

Introduction

The medicinal plants produce many chemicals that are biologically active. Some plants called botanicals are of broad-spectrum toxic effect toward insects and act as insecticides or herbicides or deter herbivores. Many plants chemicals in essential oils are containing volatile or non-volatiles, and classified into terpenes, steroids, fatty acids, saponins and alkaloid compounds. Some of these groups contain functional molecules like nitrogen-bearing molecules, such as cyanogenic

Glycosides, a very deadly poison, and saponins have two groups that are steroidal and triterpenoid. Phenols can protect against infection and herbivory by insects (Rattan, 2010). They are often anti-inflammatory and antiseptic and can have anti-viral properties. Plant oil also inhibits the feeding behavior of insects like azadirachtin, derived from the seeds of the neem tree like (Hikal *et al.*, 2017). In fact, various essential oils from plants belonging to the Lamiaceae family rich in antifungal or antibacterial compounds need to be detected. The common plant is

basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) experimental toxicity on agriculture pests, against fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), or the beet army worm *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Sa'adah *et al.*, 2024) were detected. And efficacy on many other pests were detected by Attia *et al.* (2016) to evaluate biocide activity of *Lavandula angustifolia* against *Acyrtosiphon pisum*. The mode of action of plant constituents of chemical compounds against insects is varied according to the chemical structure of the compounds. Some terpenes mode of action against pests as Eucalyptol inhibits potassium channel. Monoterpenes as linalool act as a competitive antagonist of N methyl d-aspartate receptor, with antitumor, anti-cardiotoxicity activity. Camphor is a topical anti-infective and anti-pruritic and internally as a stimulant and carminative it is poisonous anticancer and anti-viral, anti-tussive. Isoborneol has antioxidant and antiviral effect inhibitor of herpes simplex virus type. Thymol is considered antibacterial, anti-inflammatory antioxidants and antifungal agents. The endo-borneol compounds used for cerebrovascular disease and cardiovascular disease (Wojtunik-Kulesza, 2022). The mechanism of action of lavender essential oil on the insect bodies also recorded, was disruption of the molecular events (Farahat *et al.*, 2024 and Yi *et al.*, 2015). And the pupal mortality might be due to multiple mechanisms of action, including the oil blocking the pupae molting into adults. In this study, chemical compounds are identified using Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry method as well as an insecticidal activity test of *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* extractions were derived by carrying out various insect bioassays including fumigant bioassay, contact toxicity, repellent activity and its toxicity references revision.

Materials and methods

1. Plant source and essential oil extraction procedure:

The commercially available dried plant leaves of *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* obtained from markets, grinding well and macerated in ethanol (20 gm dried plant/150 ml ethanol) in flask placed over water bath placed on shaker-heater or stirrer apparatus, thermostat adjusted at 80°C, and 250 rpm for 30 min to ensure complete extraction. Then the mixture was allowed to boil for 10 min, then cooled, and filtered similar to the digestion method according to Abubakar and Haque (2020) and Bitwell *et al.* (2023). This method is suitable for extraction bioactive constituents that are readily soluble in this solvent polarity.

2. Identification of essential oil constituents analytical procedures:

At the Central agriculture pesticide Laboratories in agriculture research center, Giza, Egypt, the quantitative analyses of the essential oil of *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* constituents were analyzed by a gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), using (Agilent Technologies). Apparatus Agilent 7890 B, 5977 a MSD gas chromatography equipped with an Agilent mass spectrometric detector, with a direct capillary interface and fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.025 mm HP-5-0.25 micron -60 to 325/325°C) was used. Samples were injected under the following conditions: Helium was used as carrier gas at approximately 1 ml/min, pulsed split mode, split ratio (10:1), split flow 10 mL/min. The solvent delay was 4 min and the injection size was 1 µL. oven temperature program, 50°C for 0.5 min, then 10°C/min ramp to 190°C followed by a 10°C/min ramp to 210°C for 1 min followed by a 10°C/min ramp to 300°C and held for 2 min (total run time: 34 min) the injector temperature was set at 280°C. Finally, compounds obtained are characterized by using diverse identification techniques such as mass spectroscopy. The result is recorded as a spectrum that is percentage transmittance, and the spectra are

analyzed. The peaks obtained at certain wave numbers are compared with standard reference. The W9N11 mass spectral database was used in the identification of the separated peaks. The identification of different constituents of the two-plant oil was determined by comparing the spectrum fragmentation pattern with those stored in Wiley and NIST Mass Spectral Library (NIST, 1992).

3. Toxicity tests:

3.1. Insect sources and rearing method:

A laboratory reared strain of *Drosophila melanogaster* (Meigen) (Drosophilidae: Diptera) grown feeding on legume cocked food material were used in this study. Insect reared in plastic containers, maintained under control condition in laboratory rearing room conditioned at 27° C ±2 and 70% RH. Food additive changed and provided daily if needed (Wang and Jiang, 2024).

3.2. Contact toxicity of insecticidal assay:

Much quantity of drosophila adults releases gently to medium glass vials treated by dried film of individual extract concentrations dissolved in ethanol. A serial concentration of *L.angustifolia* and *O. basillicum* extract solution (660, 990, 1320, and 1650 ppm) were applied directly to the glass vials. On the other hand, control vials treated by ethanol only. The larvae and adult were fed with small pieces of cotton saturated by 10% sucrose. Four replicates were applied for each concentration. Mortality of both extracts on adult observed after 24 hrs. of treatment.

3.3. Repellent bioassay:

Fumigant toxicity assay was tested by using piece of cotton soaked separately in serial concentrations (660, 990, 1320 and 1650 ppm) of *L.angustifolia* and *O. basillicum* extract solution and separately placed inside plastic container 1 L capacity attached by another container by a big hole. Control container provided by piece of cotton soaked in ethanol only. Such quantity of drosophila adults was introduced smoothly and consciously into

the plastic containers. Four replicates were applied for each concentration. A piece of cotton saturated with sugar solution 10% provided for adults feeding was added. Adults in both containers were counts to attain the repellent effect after 24, 48 hrs. of the assay.

3.4. Fumigant assay:

The experimental procedure was done by using plastic containers contained piece of cotton soaked with serial concentrations (660, 990, 1320 and 1650 ppm) of *L.angustifolia* and *O. basillicum* extract solution. Small mesh iron net spherical censored placed above the piece of cotton to forbid contact adult to the extract. Piece of cotton soaked in ethanol only considered as control. Much quantity of drosophila adults introduced perfectly into the treated and the untreated container. Four replicates were applied for each concentration. A piece of cotton saturated with sugar solution 10% provided for adults feeding. Percentage of mortality due to fumigant effects was observed after 24 hrs. of treatments.

4. Statistical analysis:

Toxicity results attained by Finney Probit analysis (1971) was the estimated LC₅₀ values and its fiducial limits, slopes and intercepts by Polo-LeOra software Russell (LeOra Software, 1989) including mortality corrected according to Abbot formula (1925). The data was analyzed using SPSS 20 software to continue one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's HSD test, its results were considered significantly different at P<0.01

Results and discussions:

1. The Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) profile:

The GC-MS identification of phytochemical compounds was based on the retention time (RT), peak area, m/z, molecular formula (MF) and abundance (Ab) of detected compounds in *L. angustifolia* and *O. basillicum* extract and its composition percentage (%) are presented in Tables (1,2 and 3). A list of some compounds was found in both plant ethanol extract was found in Table (1). It

is evident from this table that all fractions have a complex chemical composition, where the major phytochemicals present in the GC-MS profile in both spectra showed presence of more mono, di, and triterpenoids. The first table exhibits some volatiles identified as o-Cymene, m, p-Cymene and cis-cymene, eucalyptol, thymol, and carvacrol. The second table showed most of detected chemicals from Superclass: Lipids and lipid-like molecules, class is prenol lipids, and subclass is monoterpinoids. Few of them is sesquiterpines like spathulenol, caryophellene oxide and epi-Bicyclosesquiphellandrene and CIS-. Alpha. -Bisabolene. The table also contains other compounds from naphthols derivatives as naphthalene-- and oxanes as eucalyptol. Similarly

Palmitic acid is fatty acids and conjugates. Also, Table (2) contains compound class is diterpinoids, sesquiterpinoids and benzoids derivatives. Hereafter both extract contained a secondary alcohols, cyclic alcohols and derivatives, monocarboxylic and carboxylic acids and its derivatives, in addition to glycoside Hydrocarbon derivatives. When comparing chemical profile of both plants based on metabolomics approach provide, structure characterization and biological activity determination using plant extraction and GC-mas compound identification were more evidence. From Farahat *et al.* (2024) GC-mass data revealed most results similar to the results of this study.

Table (1): Some terpene compounds detected in both plants *Lavandula angustifolia* and *Ocimum basilicum*.

Compounds	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>				
	RT (area)%	RT (area)%	M/z	Ab.	MF	Mass
1,8-Cineole	8.05(1.13)1.84	8.03(0.43)1.8	154.132	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
Terpan and Eucalyptol	8.05(1.13)1.84	8.03(0.43)1.8	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
Delta.3-Carene	9.33(0.42)0.68		136.12	89.38	C10H16	136.23
. Beta. -Linalool	9.369(0.28)0.46	9.46(0.6)2.55	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
Camphor	10.12(1.18)1.93	12.45(1.6)6.8	152.12	89.17	C10H16O	152.237
Endo-Borneol	10.49(1.88)3.1	10.49(0.3)1.27	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
Isoborneol	10.49(1.88)3.1	10.49(0.3)1.27	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.253
2-Propenoic acid	10.36(1.08)1.76	13.68(1.24)5.2	158.05	91.57	C7H10O4	158.15
Thymol, m-thymophenol	12.44(13.52)22.0	12.45(1.6)6.8	150.1	89.18	C10H14O	150.22
P-cymene	12.59(0.8)1.3	12.45(1.6)6.8	134.1	89.4	C10H14	134.222
. Alpha. -Terpineol	12.44(13.5)22.0	10.88(0.42)1.7	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
Cinnamic acid	10.63(1.08)1.7	13.68(1.24)5.2	148.05	90	C9H8O2	148.16
(+) Spathulenol ses	16.17(0.51)0.83	16.17(0.41)1.7	220.18	84.3	C15H24O	220.356
(-)-Caryophyllene oxide	16.247(0.26)0.43	16.24(0.33)1.4	220.18	84.3	C15H24O	220.356
(+)-epi-Bicyclosesquiphellandrene	16.88(3.4)28.4	16.88(1.92)8.2	204.18	84.5	C15H24	204.35
Alpha-cadinene	17.38(17.42)5.5	16.88(1.92)8.2	204.18	84.5	C15H24	204.35
CIS-. Alpha. -Bisabolene	17.34(1.1)1.8	15.69(0.27)1.1	222.19	84	C15H26O2	238.371
Palmitic or Palmitinic acid	20.16(0.76)1.3	20.17(8.92)39	240.24	83.11	C16H32O2	256.42

Table (2): Terpins, phenols, acids and alkaloids detected in *Lavandula angustifolia* ethanol extract.

Compound	RT	Area	%	m/z	Ab.	MF	MW
Cis-Ocimene	9.329	0.42	0.62	136.12	89.38	C10H16	136.23
Gamma. -Terpinene	9.329	0.42	0.62	136.12	89.38	C10H16	136.23
(+)-2-Bornanone	10.12	1.18	1.73	152.12	89.17	C10H16O	152.23
Dihydro coumarone and	10.67	1.25	1.84	148.05		C9H8O2	148.16
Ho-trienol or trans- (-)-	10.77	1.14	1.67	152.12	98.17	C10H16O	152.23
Carvacrol	12.59	0.8	1.18	150.1	98.18	C10H14O	150.22
Quinuclidine-4-D	12.85	0.53	0.78				
Hydrocoumarin	13.75	1.44	2.12	146.03	90.03	C9H6O2	146.14
Benzodihydropyron	13.75	1.44	2.12			C9H8O2	148.16
2,4-Dimethylthietane	15.36	1.1	1.62	74.019	91.86	C3H6S	74.14
Beta cubebene	16.88	3.64	5.35	204.18	84.5	C15H24	204.35
Rosefuran	17.04	0.36	0.53	150.1	89.19	C10H14O	150.22
(-)-Anymol	17.34	1.1	1.62	222.19	84.3	C15H26O	222.37
2-ethyldecalin	17.38	0.42	0.62	1666.1	87.37	C12H22	166.3
Herniarin	17.84	19.6	28.79	176.04	88.8	C10H8O3	176.17
Ayapanin	18.01	0.62	0.91	176.04	88.8	C10H8O3	176.17
Cuminic aldehyde	18.05	1.26	1.85	148.09	89.2	C10H12O	148.2
Pinane and Dihydropinene	18.94	0.58	0.85	138.14	89.36	C10H18	138.25
Chroman-6-ol	13.96	3.57	5.24	206.09	86.8	C12H14O	206.24
Cis-o-Coumarinic acid lactone	14.73	2.3	3.38	146.03	90	C9H6O2	146.14
Alpha.-benzopyron	14.89	0.065	0.10	146.03	90	C9H6O2	146.14
Z-Citral.Beta.- citral or Neral	14.92	0.96	1.41	152.12	89.17	C10H16O	152.23
2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol	13.96	3.57	5.24	89.06	95.12	C4H9O2	150.17
D-Fenchyl alcohol	19.97	1.49	2.19	154.13	89.13	C10H18O	154.25
2-Norbornanol	20.16	0.76	1.12	112.09	92.21	C7H12O	112.17
.Alpha.-Thujone	20.35	0.53	0.78	152.12	89.17	C10H16O	152.23
Supraene	31.10	0.57	0.84	410.39	71.4	C30H50	410.7
Sec-Butylformamide	15.17	1.95	2.86	101.08	93.9	C5H11N	101.5
Butanoic acid	15.32	0.79	1.16	88.05	95.13	C4H8O2	88.106
Iso-Propyl iso-valerate	15.32	0.79	1.16	144.11	90.9	C8H16O2	144.21
Isopropyl dodecanoate	15.36	1.1	1.62	242.22	84.05	C15H30O	242.4
2H-1-Benzopyran-2-one	13.75	1.44	2.12	146.03	90.03	C9H6O2	146.14
1H-Cycloprop[e]azulen-7-ol	16.17	0.51	0.75	156.05	88.26	C11H8O	156.18
Pinan	18.94	0.58	0.85			C10H18	138.25
10-Hydroxy-4-cadinene-3-one	19.6	1.33	1.95			C15H24O	236.35
5-Methyl-2-(3-thienyl)	19.6	1.33	1.95	175.04	84.56	C10H9N	175.25
1-Pyrrolidino-1-cyclohexene	19.8	1.34	1.97	151.13	89.04	C10H17N	150.25
Cinnamaldehyde	18.05	1.26	1.85			C10H12O	138.2
p-Tolualdehyde	10.63	1.08	1.59	120.05	91.23	C8H8O	120.15
p-Formyltoluene	10.63	1.08	1.59	120.05	91.23	C8H8O	120.15
2(3H)-Benzofuranone,3-methyl	13.75	1.33	1.95			C9H8O2	148.16
2(3H)-Benzofuranone	13.7	1.44	0.62	134.03	91.03	C8H6O2	143.13
Tetrahydro-3,6-	13.9	3.57	0.62	150.1	89.18	C10H14O	150.22
2,3-Dihydrobenzofuran	10.6	1.08	1.73	120.05	91.23	C8H8O	120.15

Table (2): Continued

Compound	RT	Area	%	m/z	Ab.	MF	MW
2-thiophene carboxaldehyde	12.85	0.53	1.84	111.99	89.65	C5H4OS	112.15
3-Thiophene carboxaldehyde	12.85	0.53	1.67	111.99	89.65	C5H4OS	112.15
Isopropyl 3-methylbutanoate	15.32	0.79	1.18	144.11	90.94	C8H16O2	144.21
9-[[[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl]amino]	15.17	1.95	0.78	132.1		C6H16N2O	132.2
2H-Benzo[f]oxireno[2,3-E]benzofuran-8(9H)-one	15.17	1.95	2.12	364.2		C21H36N2O3	364.5
3-Thujopsanone	19.8	1.34	2.12	220.1		C15H24O	220.35

2. Screening and analysis of terpenoid differential metabolites:

The tables also showed the most abundant compounds were camphor 1.9 and 6.8 %, Cinnamic acid 1.7 and 5.2%, 2-Propenoic acid 1.7 and 5.2, for *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* respectively, but carvacrol 1.18, (-)-Hotrienol 1.67%, Hydrocoumarin 2.12%, 2,4-Dimethylthietane 1.6%, Alpha. -benzopyron 0.1 % for *L. angustifolia* only and thymol and alpha-terpineol represent 22.0. The *O. basilicum* extract contained some important compounds such as estragole, tarragon, eugenol, stigmast, sitosterol, squalene, etc, Table (3). The determination of total terpenoids

contents in each extract, results achieved percentage of monoterpenoids 23,20%, diterpenoids 18,16 % and sesquiterpenoids 13,11% for both extracts respectively Figure (2). Consequently, the total terpenoids represented 54, 47% for each extract respectively and total phenols recorded 9,11% respectively. Search about similar results it found, Attia *et al.* (2016) found in *L. angustifolia* extract found linalyl acetate (29.95%), 1,8-cineole (13,66%), camphor (13,13%), alpha-pinene (3,14%) and terpinene-4-ol (1,54%), the mortality against *Acyrtosiphon pisum* was 25 µl.l⁻¹ of air, and increased with concentration, LC₅₀ values were 11.2 µl.l⁻¹ of air.

Table (3): Terpinoids, phenols, acids and alkaloids detected in *Ocimum basilicum* compounds.

Compound	RT	Area	%	M/z	Ab	Formula	MW
Estragole =4-allylanisole	11	2.03	2.40	148.09	89.2	C10H12O	148.2
Tarragon= P-allylanisole	11	2.03	2.40	148.09	89.2	C10H12O	148.2
Chavicol =P-allylphenol	11	2.03	2.40	134.07	90.2	C9H10O	134.17
Eugenol and methyl eugenol,	13.34	0.94	1.11	164.08	88.99	C10H12O2	164.2
trans-Caryophyllene	14.19	0.34	0.40	204.18	84.5	C15H24	204.35
Pyrotartaric acid	14.63	1.84	2.17	132.04	93.69	C5H8O4	132.1
Anisole	14.98	0.92	1.09	108.05	92.25	C7H8O	108.14
P-Allylanisole	11	2.03	2.40	148.09	89.2	C10H12O	148.2
Anisaldehyde	14.98	0.92	1.09	261.9	86.9	C7H7CIS	158.99
4-Morpholinyl aniline	16.74	0.51	0.60	162.11	88.74	C10H14N2	178.23
Neophytadiene	18.9	1.4	1.65	278.29	79.85	C20H38	278.51
Thiosulfuric acid	22.6	2	2.36	113.94	89.6	H2O3S2	114.1
. Gamma,-Sitosterol	35.9	4.8	5.67	414.38	72.01	C29H50O	414.7
Stigmast-5-en-3-ol	35.9	4.8	5.67	414.38	72,01	C29H50O	414.7
Linoleic acid and linolenic acid	22.38	11.56	13.7	280.24	81.29	C18H32O2	280.4
Squalene	31.1	0.9	1.06	410.39	71.4	C30H50	410.7

Table (3): Continued

Compound	RT	Area	%	M/z	Ab	Formula	MW
endo-2-Hydroxy-1,7,7-trimethylnorbornane	10.49	0.3	0.35	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
O-methyl-benzene=toluene	11	2.03	2.40			C7H8	92.14
Benzonitrile, 2-amino	12.14	1.5	1.77	103.04	92.16	C7H5N	103.2
Anthranilonitril = o-Aminobenzonitrile	12.24	0.41	0.48	118.05	91.8	C7H6N2	118.13
O-Cyano-Aniline= m-Aminobenzonitril	12.24	0.41	0.485	118.05	91.8	C7H6N2	118.14
p-aminobenzonitril	12.24	0.41	0.485	118.05	91.8	C7H6N2	118.14
Ethanon	14.63	1.84	2.175	166.13	88.17	C11H18O	166.26
Butanedioic acid	14.63	1.84	2.175	118.02	94.7	C4H6O4	118.08
2-Methylsuccinic acid=pyrotartaric acid	14.63	1.84	2.175	118.02	93.6	C5H8O4	132.11
2,5-Dimethylanisole	14.98	0.92	1.088	136.09	90.19	C9H12O	136.194
o-Methoxybenzaldehyde	14.98	0.92	1.088	136.05	91	C8H8O2	136.15
Benzenemethanol	14.98	0.92	1.088	108.05	92.25	C7H8O	108.14
Hydrocinnamaldehyde-Beta.-D2	15.69	0.27	0.319	134.07	90.2	C9H10O	137.17
1H-1,5-Benzodiazepine	16.17	0.41	0.485	144.068	89.78	C9H8N2	144.17
5.alpha.-Hydroxycaryophylla-4(12)diene	16.44	0.33	0.390			C15H24O	220.35
2-Amino-n-isopropyl benzamide	16.74	0.51	0.000	178.11	88.5	C10H14N2O	178.23
Alpha-Selinene	16.88	1.92	0.000			C15H24	204.35
trans-2-Dodecen-1-ol or (E)-2-Dodecenol	19.19	0.4	0.603	184.18	87.15	C12H24O	184.32
Phytol	18.9	1.4	2.270	296.3	79.62	C20H40O	296.53
n-Hexadecanoic acid	20.17	8.9	0.000	256.24	83.11	C16H32O2	256.42
Tetradecanoic acid or Myristic acid	20.17	8.9	0.473	228.2	85	C14H28O2	228.37
Benzo[H]Quinoline, 2,4-Dimethyl	35.17	0.87	1.655	207.1	84.29	C15H13N	
5-Nitrobenzofuran-2-Carboxylic Acid	35.46	1.49	10.52	207.01	89.06	C9H5NO5	207.14
1-(3-Methylphenyl)-1H-Indole	35.46	1.49	10.52	207.01	84.288	C15H13N	207.27
(E)-2-bromobutyloxychalcone	36.11	1.42	1.03	358.05	40.8	C19H19BrO2	359.3
[1,2,4]Triazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine-6-carboxylic acid	36.76	2.95	0.00	164.033	91.72	C6H4N4O2	164.12
2-P-Nitrophenyl-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-5- One	37.85	0.93	1.76	191.033	89.82	C8H5N3O3	191.14
endo-2-Hydroxy-1,7,7-trimethylnorbornane	10.49	0.3	0.35	154.13	89.15	C10H18O	154.25
O-methyl-benzene=toluene	11	2.03	2.40			C7H8	92.14
Benzonitrile, 2-amino	12.14	1.5	1.77	103.04	92.16	C7H5N	103.2

Figure (1): Total phenols, terpenoids, steroids and others group of phytochemicals detected for *Lavandula angustifolia* and *Ocimum basilicum* ethanol extract.

The variation in total monoterpenoid and diterpenoid in addition to the remaining compounds is the confirmation of the compositional profile in both plants. But the effective toxicity and the long-lasting studies of monoterpenes and others depends on the chemical structure with conjugated double bonds in their structure and according to their hydrocarbon skeleton can be divided into two main groups: terpenoids and phenylpropanoids, that can be divided according to the position of double bond to allylbenzenes (2,3-double bond) which are considered as toxic such as estragole and methyl eugenol and propenyl benzene derivatives (1,2-double bond) that are considered as relatively safe such as anethole and isoeugenol. the useful bioactive compounds in many

edible plants like basil, anise and fennel and at the same time, their negative impact on various cellular processes (Dief *et al.*, 2025).

The GC-MS data displayed peaks conforming different compounds in *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* Figures (1 and 3). Each peak represents a compound eluted at a specific retention time led to peaks identification and the percentage of each compound area calculated in relative to the total peak area of all detected compounds, by method of percentage peak area method, provides a way to estimate the relative abundance of each component. Tables of 1, 2 and 3 contain the m/z value used in mass spectrometry intended by formula was $m/z = M/Z$, where M is the mass of the ion and Z is the charge of the ion, and the m/z value= divide the mass of the ion by its charge.

Figure (2): Spectrum from Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry analysis of *Lavandula angustifolia* ethanol extract.

Figure (3) : Spectrum from Gas chromatography - Mass spectrometry analysis of *Ocimum basilicum* ethanol extract.

The two plant extract compound constituent results look like similar

3. Predicting toxicity and review:

The bioactivity of phytochemicals compound group complex and their secondary metabolites mode of action extensive studies lead to identifying its harmful level as carcinogenicity, cell damage ..etc.,as a result of exposure level to toxic compounds. The monoterpenes group of isoprene derivatives (camphor, citral, α -terpinene, pulegone, thujone, limonene, eucalyptol or linalool, lemon, or 3-carene, terpinolene and mechanism of toxicity indicate noncompetitively inhibit nicotinic acetylcholine receptor and decrease catecholamine secretion. Also, the mechanism of Na⁺, K⁺ATPase and ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase (NTPDase) that refer to the cytotoxicity, embryotoxic, neurotoxic, allergenic and genotoxic. Wojtunik-Kulesza (2022, using thymol in controlling land snail achieve effectiveness comparable to synthetic molluscicides (Ali, 2017). Neophytadiene is diterpenes, classified as a C₂₀H₃₂ molecule, have antioxidant properties doing plant defense mechanisms against environmental stressors and blocks three receptors in a

results of Ilić *et al.*, 2019 ; Ismail, 2006 and Kholiya *et al.*, 2022.

part in cancer viability, invisibility as it blocks Human A2a receptor at adenosine binding site, Human LRH1 and hERG K⁺ channel leads to inhibition of cancer proliferation and invasiveness which may act as a promising apoptotic inducer (Selmy *et al.*, 2023). Herniarin isolated from *Equisetum debile* Roxb proved the antioxidant activity (Ang *et al.*, 2019). Cadinene is a sesquiterpenes have low toxic effect, and find potential application in biopesticides development field (Ouyang *et al.*, 2015). The α -linolenic and linoleic acid isolated from *Ulva fasciata* showed toxic effects on red tide phytoplankter. Among *Aphidophycean flagellate*, *Heterosigma akashiwo*, LC₅₀ of α -linolenic acid and linoleic acid were estimated to be 0.58 and 1.91 μ g/ml respectively, whereas dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium impudicum* and *Heterocapsa circularisquama* were highly resistant and no significant toxic effects were observed up to 1,000 μ g/ml (Alamsjah *et al.*, 2007). From *Artemisia dracunculus*: the estragole, cis- β -ocimene, trans- β -ocimene, limonene, eugenol methyl ether, eugenol acetate, tarragone, eugenol,

caryophyllene oxide, and α -pinene are generally safe, but some of them can cause skin sensitization and respiratory toxicity and are potential inhibitors of the organic anion transporters OATP1,2 (Pujicic *et al.*, 2025). Phytoconstituents as fatty acids, including eicosatrienoic anti-inflammatory defense and cardio protective properties. β -Caryophyllene, is a bicyclic sesquiterpene, a bioactivator of some receptors as nitric oxide synthase and cyclooxygenase, similar to B-sesquiphellanderene is a sesquiterpines family have Francomano *et al.* (2014). But Beta sitosterol have Genotoxic and Cytotoxic consequence

(Paniagua-Pérez *et al.*, 2005). But by using recent developed software to predict individual compound toxicity against insects we found the toxicity estimation software (Test v. 4) which review of both plants extracts compound concentrations and others in water in mg/L that causes 50% growth inhibition to *Tetrahymena pyriformis* after 48 hours exposure, revealed results of toxicity about 30 compounds in *L. angustifolia* and *O. basilicum* compounds, some of IC₅₀ found in Figures (4 and 5) according to Schwöbel *et al.* (2011).

Figure (4) : Chemical structure of *Lavandula angustifolia* components and (IC₅₀ mg/L) against *Tetrahymena pyriformis*.

Figure (5): Chemical structure of *Ocimum basilicum* chemical components and (IC₅₀ mg/L) against *Tetrahymena pyriformis*

4. Biological activities and toxicity assessments of both extracts:

Data of some biological bioassay as toxicity assessments, repellency and fumigant effect were carried out against *D. melanogaster* adults, data found in Tables (3 and 4) including calculated constraints of the toxicity response against the insect exposed to the individual extract for 24, 48 and 72 hrs. The first concentration capacities were equal 660 PPM. Slopes and intercepts for both extracts showed good toxicity line fit, and toxicity data showed LC₅₀ refer to *L. angustifolia* were more efficient than *O. basilicum* by little differences (Figure 6). Whereas LC₅₀ values was 257.7, 377 at 24 hrs. of exposure, respectively (Table 4), and mortality increased with concentration

increase. Similar results found by some searchers Where Sa'adah *et al.* (2024) found that highest mortality rate of *Spodoptera exigua* was 75% at LC₅₀ of 0.007% of Basil leaf extract treatment by contact application has great potential to be a botanical insecticide for control. In addition, Awad *et al.* (2024) basil essential oil toxicity against two Noctuidae, *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel) and *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval), showed no significant difference between both insects. Omar *et al.* (2024) on the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*, the lethal concentration (LC₅₀) of cumin was 49%, 45%, and 33% lower than that of basil at the 24, 48, and 72 hrs. assessment periods.

Table (4): Data of contact toxicity test in ppm of individual extract against *Drosophila melanogaster* adults.

Extract	Hours	Slope	Intercept	LC ₅₀ (95 % CI)	LC ₉₀ (95 % CI)	χ ²
Lavender	24	1.32+0.14	1.79	257.7(136-487/6)	2378(1256-4504)	0.99
	48	1.57+0.123	1.28	231.5(133-403)	1527(877-2657)	0.98
	72	1.92+0.10	0.32	268(168-428)	1268(795-2023)	0.96
Basil	24	1.8+0.103	0.34	377(236-600)	1936(1214-3085)	0.98
	48	1.87+0.10	0.085	74.3(40-138.3)	2109(1339-3320)	0.947
	72	1.81+0.103	0.205	421(265-670)	2247(1413-3572)	0.98

Figure (6): LC₅₀ of *Lavandula angustifolia* and *Ocimum basilicum* extract toxicity after 24 hrs. of treatment to *Drosophila melanogaster* adults.

The efficiency of both extracts revealed sustainability of extracts to fight the insect attacking crops, and showed hopeful to be Ecofriendly Phyto-pesticides can use as alternatives of synthetic chemicals. Where some literature cited about affinity with some important enzyme related to toxicity and detoxification, like Awad *et al.* (2024) a molecular docking study of basil essential oil was performed to gain insight into the binding pattern between glutathione S-transferase and linalool is the most abundant compound (29.34%).

5. Fumigant and repellent studies of both extracts:

Data in Figures (7, 8, 9 and 10) showed the effect values against the concentration used at different exposure hours. The two-plant extracts exhibited little efficient of fumigant and repellent effect, and *L. angustifolia* were more efficient than *O. basilicum*. Where mortality was 22,47,68,70 and 37,59,78,77 mortality percentage in fumigant test at 24 and 48 hrs. of exposure. But *O. basilicum* 19,13,40, 54 and 33, 39,53, 60 mortality percentage of

fumigant test at 24 and 48 hours of exposure. Similar results from literature attained like. Komansilan *et al.* (2021) found that ethanolic extract of *L.angustifolia* was toxic to *Aeders aegypti* mosquito larvae at 500 ppm percentage was 100% kill, allow the potential to be developed as a biolarvicide for the *Aedes aegypti*. Similarly, Yi *et al.* (2016) determine the toxicity of 21 constituents from *L. angustifolia* essential oil by spray 6 g/L⁻¹ sprays) to susceptible and pyrethroid-resistant *Plutella xylostella* Larvae. Results were Linalool and linalool oxide (LC₅₀ = 0.016mg/cm⁻³) were the most toxic fumigant compounds and were 10.7-fold less toxic than dichlorvos to resistant larvae of *Cotesia glomerata*. The magnitude of toxicity by Farahat *et al.* (2024) found that both lavender essential oil and its nanoemulsion caused larval, pupal, and pupal-adult intermediate malformations of *Culex pipiens*, (LC₅₀, s) 133.85 and 480.78 ppm respectively, after 24 hrs. of treatment

and Attia *et al.* (2016) said that lavender oil can provide valuable pesticide activity with significantly lower LC₅₀ values against aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* by fumigation.

The study carried out to identify unknown compounds in two plants (lavender and basil) to discover if it contains toxicity feature for pest control. Compounds are identified based on their relative molecular mass and molecular weight. GC-MS device analysis provides abundant information of the attained molecules. Results proved that this method is useful in the identification of compounds based on chemical structure and molecular weight. Samples of both extracts contains a considerable amount of terpenoids, mono-, di-and sesquiterpenes. Toxicological studies against *D. melanogaster* achieved some efficiency discovered by some bioassay of toxicity tests. Literature review search refers to some components exist able to kill insects.

Figures (7 and 8) : Mortality percentage by Fumigant of *Lavandula angustifolia* extract, recorded after 24, 48 and 72 hrs. of treatment at different concentration to *Drosophila melanogaster* adults, and data of repellent effect include number of avoided individuals.

Figures (9 and10): Mortality percentage by fumigant effect of *Ocimum basilicum* extract, recorded after 24, 48 and 72 hrs. of treatment at different concentration to *Drosophila melanogaster* adults, and data of repellent effect include number of avoided individuals.

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